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(REVIEW PAPER IN NATURAL RESOURCE MANAGEMENT,)

Abstract

The total area under agroforestry in the world is estimated as one billion ha. The Cocoa crop is cultivated in agroforestry systems together with many tree species and other crop plants on the same plot. Carbon stocks in shaded agroforestry systems with perennial crops—such as coffee, rubber, and cocoa—may vary between 12 and 228 Mg ha⁻¹ and could help to mitigate climate change. The contribution of cocoa for sustainable production and the provision of ecosystem services (including carbon sequestration to abate climate change) at the landscape level has been explored in terms of the dichotomy between promoting intensive cocoa production to free natural forest areas for pure conservation (land-sparing strategy) and promoting mixed, environmentally friendly cocoa agroforestry systems, which may require a larger area due to smaller yields (wildlife-friendly farming strategy) but could reduce deforestation. The disease Cherville wilt of cocoa can be reduced as it is grown under the shade of forest trees which reduced the input cost and input of agrochemicals into the ecosystem. The inputs like biochar, fertilizers and composted organic manures may be added to increase carbon sequestration. Yield reduction due to shade trees is also discussed but if we consider the yield of shade trees, growing cocoa crops under shade is more beneficial than monoculture

Keywords: Carbon sequestration, climate change, cocoa, agroforestry

Introduction

Carbon sequestration is the process of capturing CO₂ from the atmosphere through physical, chemical and biological processes. and long-term storage of atmospheric CO₂ or forms of carbon to either mitigate or defer global warming and reduce the effect of dangerous climate change. During growth, all crops absorb CO₂ through photosynthesis and release it after harvest due to decomposition. The goal of carbon removal in agriculture is to utilize the crop residues and products such that the carbon cycle sequesters carbon permanently within the soil system by adopting farming methods to return biomass carbon to the soil and stored in it a stable state. Stern (2006) notes that deforestation alone is responsible for 18 % of the world's greenhouse gas emissions. One option to reduce deforestation and create a carbon sink is to encourage the establishment of tree-crop farming or agroforestry systems (UNFCCC, 2009; Oke *et al.*, 2011; Askia *et al.*, 2016) in the existing plantations.

Methodology: A review of the present status of C sequestration in the cocoa plantation was done with the objective to study the status of cocoa plantations in India and the world, carbon sequestration and its potential; towards climate change, Cocoa plantation and its carbon sequestration potential (review of research and reports published on cocoa), Management practices and input addition for cocoa plantation in relation with their effect on carbon sequestration, *etc.* through published sources. The review is undertaken in the topics viz., status of cocoa in India and world. Carbon sequestration and its potential for climate change. Cocoa plantation and its carbon sequestration potential (review of research and reports published on cocoa).

Status of cocoa plantations in India and the world**Table 1. Carbon sequestration in oil palm plantation (Cocoa as intercrop)**

Cropping system	Standing biomass (t ha ⁻¹)	Carbon stock (t ha ⁻¹)	Carbon sequestration (t ha ⁻¹ annum ⁻¹)
Cocoa	95	48	175
Oil palm	60	30	110
Oil Palm with Cocoa	155	78	284

From the below table (Table 2) it is clear that total biomass C stocks increased five times from the monoculture to the multi-shade tree system, total net primary production increased two times. The increase in total C stocks and net primary production under multi-shade may be due to the reduction of physical stress under tree shade Proper planning of cacao plantations under a shade tree cover allows for combining high yield with benefits for carbon sequestration and storage, production system stability under stress, and higher levels of animal and plant diversity. (Abourajab *et al.*, 2016)

Table 2. Comparison of carbon sequestration in monoculture and multishade system

Particulars	Monoculture	Multishade system	Remarks
Total biomass carbon stocks (Mg C ha ⁻¹)	11	57	Fivefold increase
Above-ground biomass (Mg ha ⁻¹)	18	100	6 fold increase

The total area under agroforestry in the world is estimated at around 1 billion ha. The cocoa crop is cultivated in agroforestry systems together with many tree species and other crop plants on the same plot.

Carbon sequestration and its potential for climate change

Methods for accomplishing carbon sequestration include mulching the soil with hay or dead vegetation. This protects soil from the sun and allows the soil to hold more water and be more attractive to carbon-capturing plants. On degraded wastelands, an increase in 1 tonnes of soil carbon will increase the crop yield by 20 to 40 kg ha⁻¹ of wheat, 10 to 20 kg ha⁻¹ of maize, and 0.5 to 1 kg ha⁻¹ of cowpeas

Cocoa plantation and its carbon sequestration potential (review of research and reports published on cocoa)

Cocoa-based agroforestry systems potential to stock huge amounts of carbon to mitigate climate change. Carbon stocks in shaded agroforestry systems with perennial crops—such as coffee, rubber, and cocoa—may vary between 12 and 228 Mg ha⁻¹ and could help to mitigate climate change (Nair *et al.*, 2009). In Central America, 24,000 ha of cocoa are grown without inorganic inputs or pesticides, plantations are small (0.25–3.0 ha) with high plant species richness and structural complexity, product diversification for own use, sale, maintenance of permanent soil cover and organic matter. These will promote soil and water conservation.

The following table explains that cocoa could be an ideal intercrop in an oil palm- cocoa-based cropping system as it could sequester more carbon than sole oil palm crop (Bhagya and Suresh, 2018)

Root biomass (Mg ha ⁻¹)	3	9	3 fold increase
Total net primary production (Mg ha ⁻¹ annum ⁻¹)	9	18	2 fold increase
Litter production (Mg ha ⁻¹ annum ⁻¹)	4.9	9.8	2 fold increase
Cocoa bean yield	2.4	1.6	Variation negligible

Table 3. Comparison of different systems for components of primary production and litter production

Cultivation system	Carbon net primary production (t ha ⁻¹ year ⁻¹)			Litter production (t ha ⁻¹ year ⁻¹)			
	Cacao	Shade trees	Total	Leaves of cacao	Leaves of shade tree	Other litter components	Total
Cacao mono	8	-	8	4.5	-	0.2	4.7
Cacao mono Gliricidia	12	2	14	2.5	1.5	0.2	4.2
Cocoa multi shade trees	7	9	16	2.4	5.5	1.5	9.4

The contribution of cocoa for sustainable production and the provision of ecosystem services (including carbon sequestration to abate climate change) at the landscape level has been explored in terms of the dichotomy between promoting intensive cocoa production to free natural forest areas for pure conservation (land-sparing strategy) and promoting mixed, environmentally friendly cocoa agroforestry systems, which may require a larger area due to smaller yields (wildlife-friendly farming strategy) but could reduce deforestation (Tscharntke *et al.*, 2011). To reduce deforestation and loss of natural forests, it is proposed to transform rustic cocoa into cocoa with productive shade (e.g. cocoa–timber systems), a controlled intensification that would nonetheless reduce biodiversity and ecological complexity. In Bahia, Brazil, a large cocoa-growing territory encompassing more than 500,000 ha of rustic cocoa (a wildlife-friendly landscape) and a few remnants of protected mature forest, intensive mono cultivation is not recommended because it will affect natural forest (Gockowski and Sonwa, 2011)

Management practices and input addition for cocoa plantations in relation to their effect on carbon sequestration

Cocoa planted under the shade with wider spacing (less density) store more carbon per unit area of soil than planting cocoa at less spacing

Figure 1. Cherelle wilt of cocoa

Table 4. Effect of different cocoa systems on number of healthy cocoa pod

No.	Particulars	Number of healthy pods
1	Monoculture (control)	8
2	As Inter crop (heavy shade)	17
3	As Inter crop (Under medium shade)	19

Tree diversity for shading cocoa plantations is recommended in cocoa farming for climate change adoption. The manipulation of the morphological and functional traits of canopy species has been used to optimize shade canopy design and could be used in cocoa to both maintain high yields and carbon stocks. To store more carbon without sacrificing cocoa yields, selection of tree species with (1) tall, cylindrical and thick stems—a tree form that may be called

(high density) without shade. Conversion of natural forest to agricultural land with cocoa planted at high density (1667 trees ha⁻¹) resulted in the historic depletion of soil organic carbon but there were gains of soil organic carbon with cocoa at lower plant density (1,111 trees ha⁻¹). Cocoa Research Institute of Ghana (CRIG) recommended that cocoa should be planted under some shade trees preferably 16 to 18 trees ha⁻¹ and at the planting density of 1,111 cocoa trees ha⁻¹ to increase carbon accumulation in soils as a way of reducing carbon dioxide emissions into the atmosphere.

Under shaded farms, litter fall is slightly reduced but the rates of decomposition of leaf litter are very slow compared to the shaded farms. Higher N and P are noticed in soils under shade than in open farms because of the efficient nutrient cycling process in shade farms. A higher incidence of Cherelle wilt was noticed in un-shaded farms. This is due to increased moisture stress because of increased evapotranspiration in the mono-cultivated farm (lack of shade) and reduced nutrient concentration in the soils due to lack of nutrient cycling to support the resistance to crop. Finally reduces crop yield in mono cultivation. Growing cocoa plants under shade enhanced better nutrient cycling, improved the fertility status of soil and disease-free pod development.

Sequoia—like *Terminalia ivorensis* in West African cocoa plantations. Large trees store most of forest aboveground biomass; tall trees cast a “lighter” shade than short trees; (2) small canopies and light foliage (like *Albizia spp.*; (3) large, deep, thick roots; and (4) rapid growth and high-density timber; (5) inverted phenology which would be of special interest (e.g. *Faidherbia albida* in Africa, which loses foliage during the rainy season and keeps it

during the dry season). This inverted phenology behaviour has been observed in *Dalbergia glomerata* (a highly valuable timber) used as shade over cocoa in Honduras. It seems possible to design cocoa plantations with high carbon stock levels and good cocoa yields.

Organic manures can be applied along with inorganic fertilizers to enhance growth and yield thereby increasing carbon sequestration. The organic manures (poultry manure and green manure) were applied at the rate of 0.56 tonnes/ha (500 g/seedling); urea and single superphosphate were applied at rates of 0.26 and 0.11 tonnes/ha, respectively.

Cocoa, 80 percent of which is cultivated by smallholders, is an export crop for many countries in Africa, and black pod disease caused by *Phytophthora spp.* is a major constraint to its production. Cocoa pod husk has been identified as a major source of inoculums of *P. megakarya* if left in farmers' fields as waste. Cocoa pod husk may be dried and burned in limited oxygen in a kiln to produce biochar. Biochar can be used as an alternative to control black pod disease and improve cocoa yields in smallholder farms while reducing farmer's spending on chemicals for black pod disease.

In the Toledo district of Belize, cocoa trees are prone to the fungal disease monilia, made worse by lack of airflow through the orchards. Pruning of trees for air circulation creates huge waste that is generally burnt resulting in emissions of atmospheric CO₂. Cut-down parts of cocoa pruning provide a sustainable source of feedstock for producing biochar. Crop fertilization in the form of biochar improves soil fertility, promotes plant growth and resistance to biotic stresses and helps to mitigate climate change (One tonne of biochar is equivalent to 2.7 tonnes of CO₂ removed from the atmosphere). In addition to this, they are raising grafted plants in nurseries, often for up to eight months before they are planted out in an orchard setting. Grafting allows for stronger rootstock to be spliced onto a superior fruiting stem – thereby increasing plant strength and yield. This means that young plants are subjected to a long period in a nursery environment, sometimes throughout the entire dry season when irrigation can be sporadic. As biochar has water retention properties, its advantages to this new, nursery-based growing system.

Biochar was mixed with locally sourced nutrients and applied to the soil around the base of semi-mature and mature trees, around the drip line and under leaf litter. Within twelve months, growers reported benefits to cocoa trees including more vigorous growth, improved flushing (Cocoa trees exhibit a flushing-type growth habit, with two to four growth flushes per year), boosted disease resilience, increased yield and earlier maturation time

Cacao farming when carried out as part of an agroforestry system with over 25% shade trees has great potential to act as a carbon sink and can sequester about 30 kg CO₂ eq. per kg of dry bean (Alluri *et al.* 2022).

The incentives to emit less and capture more greenhouse gases, such as the Joint Implementation and Clean Development Mechanisms, REDD+ (Reduced Emissions from Deforestation and Forest Degradation), and voluntary carbon markets (Christina, 2010) extended to the farmers through complete documentation of carbon sequestration. The farmers can get extra benefits for increasing carbon stock without sacrificing regular income through cocoa cultivation by the adoption of a cocoa-based agroforestry system

instead of monoculture, application of green manure, compost and biochar may boost the yield of cocoa by increasing carbon sequestration.

Conclusions

Carbon sequestration in the agroforestry system is an innovative approach to economic development for the nation from rural development with ecosystem services. The result of the study will be helpful to the Governments to promote ecosystem service programmes from cocoa production and mitigate climate change.

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